

STIFFNESS CRITICAL DAMAGE ENVELOPES FOR MULTIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE LAMINATES UNDER MULTIAXIAL LOADING CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

Load-bearing laminated structures undergo complex crack evolution processes and consequent stiffness degradation, which leads to a decline in their overall performance. Thus, consideration of damage evolution is important for stiffness critical applications. In this study, a multi-scale damage model combining synergistic damage mechanics (SDM) with an energy-based damage evolution model is developed for multidirectional laminated structures. The SDM approach combines computational finite element-based micromechanics with continuum damage mechanics, enabling the evaluation of the laminate stiffness. The damage model predicts evolution of sub-critical matrix cracks in different plies under multiaxial loading. Model predictions, which include ply crack density evolution and laminate stiffness degradation, correlate well with available experimental data, while model results for various CFRP and GFRP multidirectional laminates demonstrate its robustness. Additionally, damage envelopes corresponding to pre-selected critical stiffness degradation levels are developed to serve as an alternative to current approaches of final failure envelopes, and are regarded as a useful design tool for stiffness critical composite structures in practical applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

Laminates with multidirectional plies are often utilized in practical load bearing structures to provide comprehensive directional strength and stiffness properties. The nature of the damage evolution in these laminates under realistic multiaxial loading conditions involves the progression of through-the-thickness ply cracks in multiple orientations. The interaction of these ply cracks influence the laminate ply constraining effects (see Fig. 1), whereby a complex three-dimensional stress state ensues. Being subcritical in nature, this damage, even at high crack densities, does not typically lead to catastrophic structural failure, although they may cause the onset of critical damage modes such as delamination and fiber fracture [1]. Nevertheless, ply cracking does cause a progressive degradation of the laminate stiffness due to stress redistributions near cracks. Thus, a thorough understanding of the progressive nature of this failure process in multidirectional laminates is very important.

The common industry practice is to utilize failure theories such as the well-known Tsai-Wu criteria or Puck's criteria for the design of composite structures, without any consideration for the progression of damage or the corresponding stiffness degradation. In addition, the inability of various failure theories to accurately predict final failure envelopes was illustrated through the recent world-wide failure exercise (WWFE) [2]. A more suitable approach is to consider the progressive failure process in composite structures, whereby crack evolution and its influence on the laminate stiffness are

explicitly accounted for, and is accomplished by damage mechanics based progressive failure models. In this respect, critical stiffness criteria can be proposed as an alternate to traditional failure criteria. For many practical composite structures, such as automotive, aircraft and wind turbine structures, stiffness based criteria will be more useful.

The problem of subcritical damage evolution in laminated composites has been investigated extensively [3–5]; however most of the reported studies consider uniaxially loaded cross-ply laminates containing cracks in only the 90° plies. Ply crack evolution in multidirectional laminates has also been investigated, but only under uniaxial loading conditions [6–8]. On the other hand, the existing models that consider multiaxial loading [9–13] are not applicable to multidirectional laminates involving ply cracking in multiple orientations. This is partly due to the fact that some of them provide closed-form solutions only applicable for cross-ply laminates. Other models utilize ultimate failure criteria to predict traditional failure envelopes, without considering the actual progression of damage. Also, the practical application of many models is limited as they rely on extensive empirical data for calibration. In general, existing models fail to combine damage evolution with stiffness degradation in a coherent fashion, which renders them inadequate for the analysis of practical stiffness critical structures.

Montesano and Singh [14, 15] have recently addressed some of these modelling limitations through a multiscale progressive synergistic damage mechanics (SDM) model, wherein damage evolution in cross-ply laminates subjected to biaxial loading was predicted using an energy approach. The model combines computational micromechanics with continuum damage mechanics (CDM) for evaluating the corresponding laminate stiffness degradation. The main goal of this study is to extend this comprehensive model for the case of multidirectional composite laminates subjected to multiaxial loading, which is not a trivial task. Additional modelling considerations such as evaluation of the ply-dependent ply crack energy release rates must be accounted for, as will be outlined. To the knowledge of the authors, this is the only model reported that can predict damage evolution and stiffness degradation for multidirectional laminates under multiaxial loading conditions, which overcomes the critical limitations of the previously cited models. Furthermore, we also introduce the concept of critical stiffness damage envelopes which are generated for many multidirectional laminates. Their utility as robust and more practical design criteria for stiffness critical composite structures is discussed.

Figure 1: A representative volume element of damaged multidirectional laminate subjected to in-plane multiaxial strain state. The local transformed strain components and crack spacing are also shown.

2 ANALYTICAL MODEL

The developed multiscale model utilizes a SDM approach with an energy-based damage evolution model. The SDM model enables evaluation of the in-plane stiffness moduli for multidirectional laminates undergoing multi-mode ply cracking under multiaxial loading situations, and will be described first. An energy-based approach to predict the evolution of ply cracks in different off-axis plies under biaxial loading will be subsequently presented.

2.1 Laminate Constitutive Equations

A representative volume element (RVE) for a general multidirectional laminate consisting of cracked on-axis, off-axis and transverse plies, and subjected to a general in-plane multiaxial applied strain state is shown in Fig.1. The damage state for a specific ply within the RVE volume can be represented through a second-order tensor as [16]:

$$D_{ij}^{(\alpha)} = \frac{\kappa_{\alpha} t_{\alpha}^2}{s_{\alpha} t} n_i n_j \quad (1)$$

Here, t_{α} is the cracked ply thickness, s_{α} is the average crack spacing, and n_i are components of the crack surface normal unit vector (see Fig. 1). The κ_{α} term is a constraint parameter that represents the corresponding ply constraining effect, which is a function of the crack opening displacement (COD) and is evaluated using 3D micromechanical FE models [14]. Considering thin symmetric orthotropic laminates, the damage tensor components can be cast into the Helmholtz free energy and the cracked laminate stiffness tensor can be defined as:

$$C_{ijkl} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_x^o}{1-\nu_{xy}^o \nu_{yx}^o} & \frac{\nu_{xy}^o E_y^o}{1-\nu_{xy}^o \nu_{yx}^o} & 0 \\ \frac{\nu_{xy}^o E_y^o}{1-\nu_{xy}^o \nu_{yx}^o} & \frac{E_y^o}{1-\nu_{xy}^o \nu_{yx}^o} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{xy}^o \end{bmatrix} - \sum_{\alpha} a_{\alpha} D_{\alpha} \begin{bmatrix} 2a_1^{(\alpha)} & a_4^{(\alpha)} & 0 \\ a_4^{(\alpha)} & 2a_2^{(\alpha)} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2a_3^{(\alpha)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

The first term on the right hand side of Eq. (2) represents the stiffness matrix for the undamaged laminate evaluated using classical laminate theory (CLT), whereas the second term represents the stiffness changes brought about by damage in different modes [15].

2.2 Energy-Based Damage Evolution Model

An energy approach based on the concepts of linear elastic fracture mechanics has been developed to predict the evolution of subcritical ply cracks in multidirectional laminates subjected to multiaxial loading conditions. For brevity only the main points will be discussed here, and the reader is referred to Refs. [7, 15] for complete model development. Consider two cracks states for an arbitrarily oriented ply in a laminate with crack spacing denoted by s_{α} and $s_{\alpha}/2$ as shown in Fig. 1. Upon increasing the applied load additional cracks may form, increasing the number of cracks from N to $2N$. If energy associated with mode I is considered, the work required to close the new N cracks is defined by:

$$W_I = \frac{(\sigma_2^{\alpha})^2 t_{\alpha}}{E_2} [2\tilde{u}_n^{\alpha}(s_{\alpha}/2) - \tilde{u}_n^{\alpha}(s_{\alpha})] \quad (3)$$

Here, E_2 is the transverse modulus of the undamaged ply, σ_2^{α} is the transformed far-field ply level stress acting normal to the crack plane evaluated using CLT, and \tilde{u}_n^{α} denote the normalized average CODs associated with a specific damage mode. In order to accurately capture the crack-shielding

effect, the normalized average CODs evaluated from 3D micromechanical FE models are represented by an inverse sigmoidal function of crack density [14].

For any given loading condition, the criterion for ply crack multiplication in an arbitrarily oriented ply is defined as:

$$\frac{W_I}{G_{Ic}} \geq 1 \quad (4)$$

where G_{Ic} is the critical strain energy release rate associated with crack multiplication in mode I for a particular ply. Since the process of crack multiplication in constrained plies is quite different than individual crack extension, G_{Ic} needs to be calibrated. In order to avoid costly experimental testing, we have developed a numerical approach based on modified crack tip closure technique using a 3D micromechanical FE analysis [15]. The benefit of this numerical approach is that the distinct G_{Ic} values for crack multiplication in each ply of a laminate of any given stacking sequence can be accurately evaluated. This is important for accurately predicting crack evolution in multiple plies for a laminate subjected to multiaxial loading conditions.

The complete procedure for predicting micro-crack initiation and propagation in multiple plies for a general symmetric laminate has been coded into a MATLAB algorithm as is described in Ref. [15]. This methodology is able to predict the simultaneous evolution of ply cracks in multiple damage modes, while also accounting for crack interactions between adjacent cracked plies through the normalized COD functions.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The developed model is used to predict the evolution of ply cracks in laminates subjected to uniaxial and biaxial loading. Thereafter, damage envelopes corresponding to critical stiffness levels are predicted for a quasi-isotropic laminate. To showcase the wide utility of the developed method, a variety of CFRP and GFRP laminates were considered.

3.1 Model Predictions

Computational micromechanics through 3D FE modeling was first utilized to evaluate the normalized CODs, \tilde{u}_n^α , and to calibrate damage constants, $a_i^{(\alpha)}$, as required in Eqs. (2) – (3). The detailed analysis procedure is described in Ref. [14]. For the CFRP and GFRP laminates considered here, the ply elastic properties are summarized in Table 1. Figure 2 shows predictions of 90° ply crack density evolution and axial stiffness degradation for $[0/90]_s$ and $[0/90_2]_s$ cross-ply CFRP laminates loaded in uniaxial tension, which also includes experimental data taken from Ref. [17]. A clear agreement between model predictions and experimental data can be seen. The model is also able to predict a lower crack initiation stress for the laminate with the thicker 90° ply as reported in previous experimental studies [5]. The resulting stiffness degradation shown in Fig. 2b demonstrates the use of Eqs. (2) and (3) for each laminate, which results from crack initiation and propagation in the 90° plies. Next, damage evolution under equibiaxial tensile loading is considered for a $[\pm 45]_s$ angle-ply GFRP laminate. The predicted crack density results are shown in Fig. 3a, while Fig. 3b includes the corresponding stress-strain curve and the experimental data from Ref. [18]. The crack initiation strain predicted by our model corresponds to the reported value of 0.20% in Ref. [18], while the stress-strain curve is accurate for lower strains and deviates at strains greater than 1.2% as shown. This is likely a result of neglecting the nonlinear shear response of the off-axis plies, which may be prevalent in this laminate.

Engineering constant		CFRP ply	GFRP ply
E_1	[GPa]	144.8	46
E_2	[GPa]	11.38	13
ν_{12}	–	0.30	0.30
G_{12}	[GPa]	6.48	5.0
t_{ply}	[mm]	0.132	0.50

Table 1: CFRP and GFRP ply elastic properties.

Figure 2: Cross-ply CFRP laminate (a) predicted and experimental 90° ply crack density evolution, (b) predicted normalized stiffness degradation.

3.2 Critical Stiffness Damage Envelopes

As pointed out in the introduction, many practical composite structures have design functions that are stiffness critical. In such situations, it would be wise to develop critical damage envelopes corresponding to critical levels of stiffness properties, rather than strength characteristics. Here, we present critical stiffness damage envelopes for a $[0/90/\mp 45]_s$ GFRP laminate predicted by simulating damage evolution and stiffness degradation for various biaxial loading ratios. Since some industry practices preclude any design that allows existence of ply cracks, damage envelopes corresponding to initiation of ply cracks are also developed. Critical stiffness damage envelopes, on the other hand, represent the threshold for a particular magnitude of the laminate stiffness degradation for either the

axial, E_x , or transverse, E_y , modulus. Only in-plane stiffness changes are considered in the present model. Out-of-plane deformations may need to include delamination modelling, which is a critical damage mechanism, and is thus excluded from consideration herein.

The corresponding envelopes are presented in Fig. 4 for the $[0/90/\mp 45]_s$ GFRP laminate. The shape of the crack initiation envelope results from the fact that the 90° ply cracks are critical when the biaxial stress ratio $\sigma_x / \sigma_y > 1$, while the 0° ply cracks are critical when $\sigma_x / \sigma_y < 1$. For the damage envelope corresponding to 10% stiffness reduction, the longitudinal and axial stress components both drive cracking in the 45° plies during biaxial loading. The increased local normal ply stress components cause ply cracks to initiate and saturate much sooner, thus the shape of the 10% stiffness reduction damage envelope is approximately linear as shown.

Figure 3: Equibiaxially loaded $[\pm 45]_s$ GFRP laminate (a) predicted crack density evolution, (b) predicted and experimental stress-strain response.

Figure 4: Biaxial crack initiation and critical stiffness envelopes for $[0/90/\mp 45]_s$ GFRP laminate.

3.3 Discussion

The ability of the developed model to predict damage evolution and stiffness degradation for various multidirectional laminates under multiaxial loading has clearly demonstrated its robustness. The proposed concept of using critical stiffness damage envelopes, in lieu of failure envelopes, as design criteria for stiffness critical structures is an important contribution of this work. However, there are some limitations with the model which are worth discussing at this stage. First, the model does not currently account for ply nonlinear shear stress-strain behaviour. For angle-ply laminates this may contribute to their overall stress-strain response, which may improve the stress-strain predictions presented in Fig. 3b. Secondly, the model does not currently account for the effects of crack sliding displacements (CSD) for evaluation of the stiffness tensor defined by Eq. (2). It is not clear at this stage whether or not the addition of CSDs will greatly influence the stiffness predictions for other laminate configurations not studied here. Finally, compressive damage modes are currently not considered by the model. It is clear that matrix cracks will still be the first sub-critical damage modes, but the evolution of these cracks under compressive loading must be investigated further.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented the predictions of a developed multiscale progressive damage model, where the behaviour of various multidirectional laminates subjected to multiaxial loading was studied. The model combined computational micromechanics with continuum damage mechanics in a synergistic damage mechanics framework to evaluate the corresponding laminate stiffness degradation, whereby the computational micromechanical model inherently accounted for crack interactions and ply constraining effects. This is seen as a clear advantage over existing models since it eliminated the need for costly empirical calibration. Furthermore, an energy-based approach was utilized to predict the evolution of sub-critical ply cracks under multiaxial loading. This model accounted for the variation of critical strain energy release rate, G_{Ic} , for ply cracks in the different laminate plies. This is an advantage over existing models that assume constant G_{Ic} for all plies, and is important requirement for multiaxial loading conditions. The model predictions correlated well with available experimental data for various GFRP and CFRP laminates, providing validation for the developed model. In addition, the new concept of critical stiffness damage envelopes was presented as a suitable design criterion for stiffness critical composite structures, where failure is not defined in the traditional sense as a loss in load bearing capacity, but rather when a critical stiffness or a maximum deflection of the structure is attained.

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